

THE BLAST RESISTANCE OF DYNEEMA COMPOSITE BEAMS UNDER SHOCK LOADING

K. Kandan^{1*}, B.P. Russell¹, V.S. Deshpande¹ and N.A. Fleck¹

¹ Department of Engineering, Cambridge University, U.K

* Corresponding author (kk412@cam.ac.uk)

Keywords: *Dyneema composite, Carbon fibre/epoxy composite, blast resistance and shock loading*

1. Introduction

High performance composites made from Ultra High Molecular weight Polyethylene (UHMwPE) are finding increasing application in light weight armour systems. These materials possess fibre strengths several times than that of steel and densities less than water, making these some of the highest specific strength materials commercially available [1]. One example of this class of material is the Dyneema[®] HB26 composite plate manufactured by DSM[®] [2].

Dyneema[®] finds extensive use in the armour protection industry and much research has focused on the ballistic performance of UHMwPE composites [3]. However, the question of what makes these particular composites good armours remains unresolved. Of interest is the performance of these armours against shock loading such as explosions and near miss explosions. This has not been previously explored in the open literature.

The objective of this work is to investigate the blast response of ballistic grade Dyneema HB26 composite beams under simulated shock loading. It is compared with equal areal mass of composite beams in two different states: a) Carbon fibre/epoxy composite where resin is cured and b) Carbon fibre/epoxy composite pre-preg. This work sets out to determine some of the key mechanisms that enable Dyneema composites to perform so well.

2. Materials and dynamic testing

2.1 Materials

Three material systems are compared: Dyneema HB26, Carbon fibre (IM7)/epoxy (fiberite 934) in which the resin is cured (CF Composite), and the same carbon/epoxy system in its pre-cured state (CF

Composite pre-preg). Beams were constructed from alternative layers of 0° and 90° plies lay-up such that each material system had the same areal mass (5.89 kg m⁻²). Dyneema composite material was supplied by DSM, Netherlands and Carbon fibre/epoxy pre-preg material was supplied by Hexcel Composites, U.K.

2.2 Dynamic testing

Dyneema and Carbon fibre/epoxy beams were subjected to simulated localised shock loading by impacting metal foam projectiles. This technique was developed by D.D Radford et al. [5] to ascertain the blast resistance of beams under simulated shock loading. ALPOROS aluminium metal foam projectiles (relative density ~11%) having diameter of 28.5 mm and length of 50mm were fired from single stage gas gun at a range of velocities: 140-550 ms⁻¹, resulting the localised blast impulse of 1 - 5 kPa s. The experimental set-up used for the blast loading of the beams is shown in Fig. 1. Both ends of beam were through bolted and clamped between the back support and top metal plate as seen in Fig. 1. The free span and width of the beam are 200 mm and 35 mm respectively. The Dyneema, CF composite and CF composite pre-preg beam thicknesses are 6, 3.75 and 4.5 mm respectively. High speed photography is used to capture the beam dynamic deformation during shock loading.

2.3 Measurements

The beams were marked where they entered the support in order to observe any movement of the beam that might occur, such as the beam pulling out of the support. Thus, the distance between these markers defines the free span of the beam, L_0 . High speed photography could then be used during the experiment to extract both the arc length between the boundary markers, L_m , and the arc length between the supports, L_s . The back face deflection, δ

was also captured in this way. These quantities are shown graphically in Fig. 2. The change in length of a beam subject to a shock loading is composed of two contributions, that due to strain within the beam, l_e defined as:

$$l_e = L_m - L_0 \quad (1)$$

and that from material pull out from the support, l_p defined as:

$$l_p = L_s - L_m \quad (2)$$

Thus the total length change of the beam can be written:

$$l = l_e + l_p$$

Dividing through by the original length of the beam, L_0 we can write the non-dimensionalised form:

$$\bar{l} = \phi + \varepsilon$$

Where the terms here are strain-like quantities: ϕ is the pull-out fraction and ε is strain.

A Phantom V12 camera (Vision Research, NJ07470, and USA) with inter-frame time of 25.63 μs and exposure time of 1 μs , was used to capture the experiments.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Blast performance

Peak back-face deflection at mid-span is plotted against applied impulse and shown in Fig. 3 for all beams. Blast performances of the beams were evaluated by maximum sustained impulse. The Dyneema beams failed at impact velocity of 397 ms^{-1} , whereas CF composite beam in which resin was cured failed at impact velocity of 280 ms^{-1} . The CF composite pre-preg beams where resin is in the pre-cured state failed at impact velocity of 558 ms^{-1} . Thus, the CF composite pre-preg beam is improved by a factor of two by not curing the epoxy matrix, and even outperforms the Dyneema material. A strong influence of the matrix properties is seen on the blast resistance of the composite material.

3.2 Deformation mechanism

An image sequence of the cured CF composite beam under shock loading is shown in Fig. 4. Initially localised deformation beneath the projectile is observed and then a flexural wave laterally propagates towards ends of the beam and then reflects back. Fibre fracture is observed where the beam is supported. Delamination between composite plies occurs after the fibre failure where it is supported.

The Dyneema and CF composite pre-preg beams both deform in a similar manner. This can be broken into two stages. First, highly localised deformation is observed in the beam directly under the projectile which propagates as a shear wave towards ends of the beam. Delamination is seen in the wake of the shear wave (Fig. 5 and 6). Notice that the black vertical marker lines drawn on the Dyneema beam remain vertical as the beam undergoes deformation. This indicates that the beam undergoes only shear deformation. Second, when the shear wave reaches the support, the beam enters a membrane stretching mode.

The Dyneema beam fails in a tension mode. Failure is seen within the support where it is reduced in cross sectional area due to bolt holes in the beam. The CF composite pre-preg beam failure is observed as the composite plies slip from the support.

3.3 Influence of shear strength

A trend is observed here, whereby increased shock loading performance is seen as the matrix shear strength is reduced. There are a number of mechanisms that arise from a low shear strength that enable this enhanced performance. First, we see a transition from a bending or flexural wave, to a shear wave, as the matrix shear strength is reduced. As the matrix shears, this acts as a load limiter such that the fibres do not see loads close to their failure load during the initial stages of deformation. In a beam with high shear strength, load is transferred across the section of the beam and the outer fibres will see a much higher load than those along the neutral axis.

Second, as the beam enters the membrane stretching mode, the fibres begin to pick up load. As a result of

the initial shearing stage, the fibres are more uniformly loaded and each ply will reach failure at a similar time. In contrast to this, the high shear stiffness beam will fail at the outer plies at a much earlier stage due to the bending stresses already present.

There is also a geometric strengthening effect that comes into play. During this shearing process, the plies have rotated such that they are more efficient at carrying the applied load, F . The maximum load supported by the beam is given by:

$$F = 2T\sin\theta \quad (3)$$

Where, T is the tension in the beam and θ the angle that the plies make with the original beam position, Fig. 7.

3.4 Influence of beam lengthening

Referring back to equation (3) it is apparent that if we increase the lengthening of the beam, we shall also increase the angle θ .

A further consequence of low shear strength is that the beam is more inclined to pull-out from its support, as the matrix yields more easily along this support interface. Also, in the case of the Dyneema material, there is very low coefficient of friction.

Both the Dyneema and CF composite pre-preg beams exhibit significant pull-out from the supports during loading. This lengthening due to pull-out is plotted along with the lengthening due to material stretching as a function of time, in Fig. 7. Non-dimensional quantities ϕ, ε are plotted on the left y axis and the dimensional quantities l_e, l_p on the right.

At the velocity of 150 ms^{-1} the Dyneema beam experiences only pullout and no stretching is observed. In the CF uncured beam, the pull out is similar and only a small amount of stretching is seen, Fig. 8a. As the velocity is increased (to 350 ms^{-1}), the pull-out is also increased and the material experiences significantly more stretching, Fig. 8b.

Lengthening due to pull-out is the larger of the two contributing factors to the overall length change of the beam, and so the greater influence on θ .

3.4 Improving the performance

Several mechanisms for improving the shock loading performance have been identified. Ultimate resistance to failure is provided by the high strength fibres; however, the matrix plays a significant role influencing how effectively the fibres are able to sustain load.

Thus, to produce a superior ballistic system it is desirable to change the constituent properties of the composites in the following manner, such to increase the value of F in equation (3).

Increasing the fibre strength σ_f will allow the beam to carry a greater tension T across its section. Increasing the failure strain of the fibre, ε_f will enable greater lengthening, increasing the angle θ . Reducing the shear strength of the matrix material τ_m enables two things: first, a more uniform stress distribution across the beam section by the elimination of bending stresses (increasing T); second, is likely to promote greater slip at the boundary, again increasing the angle θ .

4. Conclusion

The blast response of Dyneema beams was investigated under simulated shock loading. This study suggests that the role of matrix properties has a very significant influence in the Dyneema beam blast resistance in addition to the UHMwPE fibre properties.

It is demonstrated that the UHMwPE fibre reinforced in complaint matrix Dyneema composite promotes: a) shearing and membrane stretching mode deformation and b) geometry effect pull-out. This pull-out gives a significant contribution to the length change of the beam during deformation, enhancing the strength through a geometry effect.

Comparison of two carbon fibre systems, one in which the matrix is fully cured and the other where the matrix remained in the pre-preg state, were fabricated to assess the matrix influence. The simple reduction in matrix shear strength that this achieved enabled the uncured composite to sustain a higher impulse than that of the Dyneema composite.

References

- [1] J.L.J Van Dingenen, "High performance Dyneema fibres composites". *Materials & Design*, Vol. 10, No 12, pp 101-104, 1991.
- [2] DSM Dyneema B.V. Mauritslaan 49, 6129 EL Urmond, The Netherlands.
- [3] M.J.N. Jacobs, J.L.J Van Dingenen, "Ballistic protection mechanisms in personal armor". *Journal of materials science*, Vol. 36, pp 3137-3142, 2001.
- [4] D.D. Radford, V.S. Deshpande and N.A. Fleck, "The use of metal foam projectiles to simulate loading on a structure", *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, Vol. 31, pp 1152-1171, 2005.

Fig. 1: Experimental setup and boundary conditions used to ascertain blast resistance of the beam under simulated shock loading.

a) Beam un-deformed configuration

b) Beam deformed configuration

Fig. 2: Schematic of beam un-deformed and deformed configuration showing a) beam un-deformed length (L_0), b) beam deformed arc length between the markers (L_m), c) beam deformed arc length between the supports (L_s) and d) back face deflections (δ).

Fig. 3: Summary of peak deflection vs. impulse for a) Dyneema HB26, b) Carbon fibre (IM7)/epoxy (fiberite 934) in which the resin is cured, and the same carbon/epoxy system in pre-preg state.

Fig. 5: Montage of high speed image sequences of HB26 Dyneema composite beams at impact velocity of 397 ms⁻¹.

Fig. 4: Montage of high speed image sequences of Carbon fibre/epoxy composite beams at impact velocity of 280 ms⁻¹.

Fig. 6: Montage of high speed image sequences of Carbon fibre/epoxy composite pre-preg beams at impact velocity of 394 ms⁻¹.

Fig. 7: The beam schematic indicating the resistive force, tension in beam and the angle between beam longitudinal axis and deformed state increases

a) Impact velocity $v_i = 150 \text{ ms}^{-1}$

b) Impact velocity $v_i = 350 \text{ ms}^{-1}$

Fig. 8: Lengthening (by pull-out and material stretching) plotted against time for Dyneema composite and Carbon fibre/epoxy pre-preg beams at impact velocity of (a) 150 ms^{-1} and (b) 350 ms^{-1} .